

Hubei Civet Cats Were Not Infected with SARS1:

Reanalysis of 2005 paper demonstrates PCR artifacts were improperly interpreted as positive for infection

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper was to reanalyze the evidence in a paper from 2005 that SARS1 was identified in farmed civet cats from Hubei Province, where Wuhan is located. The conclusions of the reanalysis study are:

1. All studies other than the 2005 paper found that SARS1 was not found in civet cats located on farms. This involved ten papers, 33 farms in 12 provinces, including Hubei, and 1236 civet cat samples. The calculated 95% Confidence Interval for the incidence of SARS1 in farmed civet cats was from 0 to 0.24%. The finding of SARS1 in Hubei farms in the 2005 paper was, if true, a highly statistically significant outlier finding.
2. The 2005 paper used a bespoke RT-PCR assay that was validated with five authentic human SARS1 specimens. Authentic human specimens in this assay had three characteristics:
 - a. All three genes, the N gene, ORF3, and ORF8, were present.
 - b. The Ct values for these three gene products ranged from 34 to 38.
 - c. The stoichiometry of the three gene products, expressed as the ratio of ORF3/N gene, of ORF8/N gene, and of ORF8/ORF3, were highly regular with standard deviations of only 4% to 8%.
3. The seven civet specimens were examined using the above three characteristics and none of them meet these three characteristics for a clinical infection.

Based on this reanalysis of the 2005 Hu et al. paper, it is concluded that this study does not support a finding that SARS1 was found in civet cats from farms in Hubei province. Since this study has been used as evidence that farmed civet cats in Hubei could be a plausible intermediate host for the SARS-CoV-2 virus, this reanalysis brings into question the use of this data as evidence for a plausible host for SARS-CoV-2.

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Introduction

One method of creating evidence that SARS-CoV-2 was a zoonotic spillover from market animals to humans in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, is to use findings from the SARS1 epidemic, which is an agreed market spillover, to support certain hypotheses. Since both SARS1 and SARS-CoV-2 have backbone sequence homology to sarbecoviruses found >1000 Kms from Wuhan, in bats from Yunnan Province, China, or northern Laos, but not bats found in Hubei Province, the need for an intermediate host from Hubei Province is required.

A 2005 paper² purporting to show civet cats from western Hubei were infected with a sarbecovirus that could be detected by PCR with primers to SARS1 has been used as evidence that farmed civets in Hubei could also be a plausible source for the SARS-CoV-2 virus.

The purpose of this manuscript is to conduct a reanalysis of this paper.

Results.

With SARS1, civet cats were infected in trading markets but not on farms.

The investigation of the origins of the SARS1 epidemic quickly came to an important conclusion: while civet cats in markets where human cases were found had high, almost universal infection rates, the farms from which these same civet cats came were devoid of SARS1 infected cats.³ In this referenced study, three markets were found to have RT-PCR positive SARS1 in 99 out of 104 civets while seven farms had only 2 positive SARS1 infections in 1245 civets or an infection rate of 0.2%.

Another study⁴ was summarized thus:

“Using three different assays, we examined 103 serum samples collected from different civet farms and a market in China in June 2003 and January 2004. While civets on farms were largely free from SARS-CoV infection, ≈80% of the animals from one animal market in Guangzhou contained significant levels of antibody to SARS-CoV, which suggests no widespread infection among civets resident on farms, and the infection of civets in the market might be associated with trading activities under the conditions of overcrowding and mixing of various animal species.”

² Hu W, Bai B, Hu Z, Chen Z, An X, Tang L, Yang J, Wang H, Wang H. Development and evaluation of a multitarget real-time Taqman reverse transcription-PCR assay for detection of the severe acute respiratory syndrome-associated coronavirus and surveillance for an apparently related coronavirus found in masked palm civets. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2005 May;43(5):2041-6. doi: 10.1128/JCM.43.5.2041-2046.2005. PMID: 15872219; PMCID: PMC1153763.

³ Shi Z, Hu Z. A review of studies on animal reservoirs of the SARS coronavirus. *Virus Res.* 2008 Apr;133(1):74-87. doi: 10.1016/j.virusres.2007.03.012. Epub 2007 Apr 23. PMID: 17451830; PMCID: PMC7114516.

⁴ Tu C, Crameri G, Kong X, Chen J, Sun Y, Yu M, Xiang H, Xia X, Liu S, Ren T, Yu Y, Eaton BT, Xuan H, Wang LF. Antibodies to SARS coronavirus in civets. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2004 Dec;10(12):2244-8. doi: 10.3201/eid1012.040520. PMID: 15663874; PMCID: PMC3323399.

The collected data of RT-PCR testing on the farms for SARS1 is contained in the following Text-Table:

Entity	Location of Collection	Collection Date	RT-PCR	Publication
Farm	Qianguan (Guangdong)	January, 2004	0/9	Tu et al. (2004)
Farm	Shanguan (Guangdong)	January, 2004	0/10	Tu et al., 2004
Farm	Shanwei (Guangdong)	January, 2004	0/10	Tu et al. (2004)
Farm	Zhuhai (Guangdong)	January, 2004	0/10	Tu et al. (2004)
Farm	Guangzhou (Guangdong)	May, 2003	2/9	Tu et al. (2004)
Farm	(Jiangxi)	May, 2003	0/15	Tu et al. (2004)
Farm	Hubei Province	January-September, 2004	0/102	Kan et al. (2005)
25 Farms	(11 Provinces)	January-September, 2004	0/1050	Kan et al. (2005)
Wild	Hong Kong	2003-2004	0/21	Poon et al. (2005)
Farm	(Hubei)	April, 2004	6/7	Hu et al. (2005)

Looking at all data except the final row, one sees that the farms had 2 SARS1 positive animals out of 1236 tested or a 0.16% SARS1 incidence. If we exclude the only farm with a positive value, the Guangzhou farm, and re-run the negative data only, one is left with zero infections out of 1227 tested animals. Based on the “rule of three”⁵ these data provide a 95% Confidence Interval for the incidence of SARS1 positive civet cats on farms of 0 to 0.24%.

Considering this incidence, the data from the Hubei farm collected in April 2004 with six cats out of seven being positive for SARS1 by RT-PCR would be an extreme outlier. This could not be because of the location in Hubei because the other data contains one test of 102 animals from Hubei province, all of which were negative. This data alone places a 95% CI upper limit of about 3%.

This leaves the RT-PCR assay itself as the potential source for this outlier.

The Hu et. al. 2005 paper uses a unique RT-PCR assay.

The authors wrote: “We have developed a multitarget real-time Taqman reverse transcription-PCR (RT-PCR) assay for the quantitative detection of SARS-CoV. The sequences of the Taqman probes with a minor groove binder and the corresponding primers were based on the sequences of the N gene, open reading frame (ORF) 3, and ORF 8.”

In validating the sensitivity of the assay, the following Figure shows the Ct relationship to virus copy number per milliliter:

⁵ Hanley, J. A.; A. Lippman-Hand (1983). "If nothing goes wrong, is everything alright?". *JAMA*. **249** (13): 1743–5. doi:10.1001/jama.1983.03330370053031. PMID 6827763. S2CID 44723518

The above data and the high correlation of the three genes allows a calculation that the Threshold Cycle for a one TCID₅₀ viral load per milliliter is 34.5 for the N gene, 36.0 for the ORF3 gene, and 36.5 for the ORF8 gene.

Human clinical infections by this new RT-PCR assay are characterized by having all three gene products in high concentration and with a fixed stoichiometry among them.

The assay was validated using five specimens taken from known SARS1 infected human patients. The five specimens had all three of the tested gene products. They were also present in relatively high concentrations, ranging from lowest Ct values of 33.99 to 38.34. A Ct of 38.34 for ORF8 is a concentration of one virus particle in 1.5 mL.

Finally, as would be expected from the coordinated transcription of the three gene products in a true infection⁶, the ratio of the three gene transcripts would be tightly controlled, as shown in the three right-hand columns.

Specimen Number	N Gene	ORF3 Gene	ORF 8 Gene	ORF3/N	ORF8/N	ORF8/3
Human 1	30.06	37.49	38.34	1.2	1.3	1.02
Human 2	28.46	35.54	36.76	1.2	1.3	1.03
Human 3	13.3	18.42	18.22	1.4	1.4	0.99
Human 4	10.95	15.67	15.63	1.4	1.4	1.00
Human 5	33.99	36.25	37.74	1.1	1.1	1.04
				1.3 +/- 0.1	1.3 +/- 0.1	1.02 +/- 0.02

⁶ [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/ebiom/article/PIIS2352-3964\(23\)00234-7/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/ebiom/article/PIIS2352-3964(23)00234-7/fulltext) Comparative subgenomic mRNA profiles of SARS-CoV-2 Alpha, Delta and Omicron BA.1, BA.2 and BA.5 sub-lineages using Danish COVID-19 genomic surveillance data.

No civet cat specimen meets the criteria seen with a human infection, that is, all three gene products in high concentration and with proper stoichiometry.

The civet data is in the following Text-Table:

Specimen Number	N Gene	ORF3 Gene	ORF 8 Gene
Civet 81	29.13	ND	ND
Civet 84	ND	ND	ND
Civet 85	22.57	41.28	40.34
Civet 88	28.06	ND	ND
Civet 252	ND	27.72	42.66
Civet 256	ND	41.89	43.29
Civet 258	ND	ND	42.16

Civet 81. Civet 81 has only one of the three gene products, the N gene. Given the stoichiometry of the human specimens above, the Ct of the ORF3 and ORF8 genes should be 37.9 and not ND, which implies >45. Using a Ct of 45 yields a ratio of ORF3/N gene and ORF8/N gene of 1.5 which is two standard deviations above the expected mean, yielding a p value of 0.05 for the probability this was a chance finding. These data are not evidence of a SARS1 infection.

Civet 84. Civet 84 has none of the three gene products and is thus not infected with SARS1.

Civet 85. Civet 85 is the only civet cat to have all three gene products registered. However, the Ct value for the ORF3 gene is \log_2 3.79 less than the lowest human infection and for the ORF8 gene is \log_2 2 less than the human infection. This indicates there is significantly less of these gene products than are seen in an authentic human infection. More importantly, the ratios of the ORF genes to the N gene are both 1.8, which is five standard deviations away from the mean value of 1.3. These data are not evidence of a SARS1 infection.

Civet 252. Civet 252 only has two of the three gene products and one of them, ORF8 is a lower level than the lowest human specimen by a \log_2 of over 4. In addition, all human specimens have a ratio of ORF3 to ORF8 gene of 1.02 +/- 0.02 while here in this specimen the ratio is 1.5. This is 25 standard deviations from the mean and is statistically an impossibility to be by chance. The Ct of the ORF3 gene of 27.72 should be from a specimen with an N gene Ct of 21.3 and should have therefore been easily detected. These data are not evidence of a SARS1 infection.

Civet 256. Civet 256 has only two of the three gene products detected but at very low levels. The ORF3 and ORF8 genes are at significantly higher Ct values than authentic human infections. The implied N gene Ct, given the human ratios and the ORF3 gene Ct value of 41.89, should have been 32.2 and not Not Detected or >45. Using a best-case value for the N gene of 45, the ORF3/N gene ratio is 0.93, which is greater than three standard deviations below the mean for a human infection, giving a p value of <0.01 that this was by chance. These data are not evidence of a SARS1 infection.

Civet 258. Civet 258 has only one of the three gene products, ORF8. The Ct value of 42.16 is significantly higher than the highest authentic human specimen. Given this Ct value for the ORF8 gene product, the expected Ct for the N gene should have been 32.4, an easily detectable value. The implied ratio of ORF8 to the N gene of >45 Ct is 0.94, which is greater than three standard deviations from the expected mean for an authentic human infection. These data are not evidence of a SARS1 infection.

Discussion

The purpose of this paper was to reanalyze the evidence in a paper from 2005 that SARS1 was identified in farmed civet cats from Hubei Province, where Wuhan is located. The conclusions of the study are:

4. All studies other than the 2005 paper found that SARS1 was not found in civet cats located on farms. This involved ten papers, 33 farms in 12 provinces, including Hubei, and 1236 civet cat samples. The calculated 95% Confidence Interval for the incidence of SARS1 was from 0 to 0.24%. The finding of SARS1 in Hubei farms in the 2005 paper was thus a highly statistically significant outlier finding.
5. The 2005 paper used a bespoke RT-PCR assay that was validated with five authentic human SARS1 specimens. Authentic human specimens in this assay had three characteristics:
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